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A grayscale, high-contrast image of a train platform with people waiting. The image is partially obscured by a large yellow triangle on the left side.

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Business, Economics & Management

- *Accounting & Taxation*
- *Business, Economics & Management (general)*
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- *Human Resources & Organizations*
- *International Business*
- *Marketing*
- *Strategic Management*
- *Tourism & Hospitality*

RECOVERY AS A RESOURCE-SAVING OPPORTUNITY

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According to reliable sources, after the first severe reality of the Covid pandemic in Europe and the stabilization of the situation in more or less, the full development of transport, resumption of flights, activation of other sectors of the economy followed by a steady rise in prices for energy carriers. A set of directives adopted by the EU at the time provided for the requirements of the new "green economy" of life and the intensive use of energy-efficient technologies, primarily to replace energy from traditional sources with renewable energy sources. Given these requirements, every country in Europe has its own strategy for achieving the goals set in this direction. , In terms of finding and introducing technical innovations. An average 10% increase in the price of gas and, consequently, a significant increase in the consumer price of electricity, together with a factor hindering the rise in prices and economic growth, provide significant motivation for the more intensive creation of renewable energy sources and the development of energy efficient technologies. Since the first steps were taken in the direction of introducing energy efficient technologies in construction in the 1970s, various types of technical means have been created, the closest types of building packaging materials have been created, construction technologies have been developed, which enable energy savings in construction and operation of buildings. There are no details when developing a strategy and selecting the technical means to achieve the desired result, globally, all the methods and technical means that are used for heating, cooling and consuming hot water by the body are even 1 watt. Allows energy savings. During the operation of any type of building, the largest amount of energy comes from heating them. Ensure the detection and proper packaging of uncontrolled energy loss sites for heating. Any type of building premise will definitely require ventilation. Traditional heating of ventilated buildings is a case of forced heat loss. In order to avoid heat loss often in domestic conditions, buildings are not ventilated, which is often the cause of the second extreme nuisance. Especially at night, the amount of oxygen in the air inside the building decreases, it is replaced by carbon dioxide, which is naturally extremely unfavorable for the health of the people there. As early as the 17th century, experiments on small animals made it clear that the cause of death was "unknown particles" emitted by the Silent and characterized by simple operating conditions. Recently, it has become important to equip buildings with intelligent engineering systems, this green construction is a special direction. Recuperators have emerged who work on the principles of sound engineering systems, such devices themselves according to the nature of the air pollution inside the building themselves choose at the time of switching on and determine the duration of the working period. This ensures the ability to effectively manage the system with maximum energy savings without human intervention. The recuperator has a special function from the combination of engineering systems required to ensure the energy efficiency of buildings, it provides a small amount of energy required for its operation, significant energy savings for heating indoor spaces and allows constant fresh air supply to indoor spaces. It should be noted that in many places, including Georgia, the Law on Energy Efficiency has been adopted. Before the law was adopted, consistent steps were taken by businesses to meet public demand. This has improved the living conditions inside the

building, saved energy, but it is unfortunate that in order to fully manage this process, there are no household recuperators on the market and therefore there is no demand, which does not make energy efficient Ability to provide full. Green construction and therefore energy efficiency is an important challenge facing the modern society, there are no minor and secondary issues in order to ensure proper results in this direction, and to achieve the result Life expectancy results. Public opinion essentially determines the timeliness of the realization of the goals and ensuring the appropriate quality in this direction. burning of candles in a closed building. The poor condition of people in spaces is caused by excessive amounts of carbon dioxide. 1982 Tesla-designed electric fan revolutionizes the ability to supply fresh air to different types of buildings. Ventilation of buildings in terms of energy efficiency must meet new requirements, at this time there should be no decrease in temperature during heating of the building, this is possible by recuperators. Air recuperation - an energy-saving feature of modern ventilation systems. This device transmits heat (energy) from the exhaust air to the incoming air. This often saves up to 40% of energy when heating a building. Recuperation is a type of green technology without which the purification of the accumulated air inside the building by the expulsion of this air produces with it the loss of energy converted into heat in the form of heat. Recuperators do not replace the boiler or other heating system, but create efficient conditions for their operation. Recuperators generate significant energy savings in living spaces, while these spaces are provided with constantly renewable fresh air, which is especially important in the conditions of the production area so that the staff working there can be provided with fresh air with heat for a reasonable period of time. This in turn provides a work environment that meets the right requirements, in such conditions labor productivity increases, production risks and production cases decrease. There are different types of recuperators working on different principles, at this time the main requirement is to choose the systems that work as much as possible.

Health & Medical Science

- Addiction
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- Alternative & Traditional Medicine
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- Immunology
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- Nuclear Medicine, Radiotherapy & Molecular Imaging
- Nursing
- Nutrition Science
- Obesity
- Oncology
- Ophthalmology & Optometry
- Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
- Orthopedic Medicine & Surgery
- Otolaryngology
- Pain & Pain Management
- Pathology
- Pediatric Medicine
- Pharmacology & Pharmacy
- Physical Education & Sports Medicine
- Physiology
- Pregnancy & Childbirth
- Primary Health Care
- Psychiatry
- Psychology
- Public Health
- Pulmonology
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- Rehabilitation Therapy
- Reproductive Health
- Rheumatology
- Social Psychology
- Surgery
- Toxicology
- Transplantation
- Tropical Medicine & Parasitology
- Urology & Nephrology
- Vascular Medicine
- Veterinary Medicine
- Virology
- Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery

INTERSTITIAL HIGH-DOSE-RATE BRACHYTHERAPY FOR LIP CARCINOMA

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Despite the number of recommendations for insertion of applicators in HDR brachytherapy, many questions regarding the applicators setting, dose normalization and its value are still under discussion. Not a randomized trial comparing the efficacy of standard fractionation modes with the other ones. The choice of dose and normalization is usually based on the volume of the tumor, histology, data from diagnostic tests. Prophylactic dose is usually applied to the entire lip and treatment dose – to the apparent tumor.

The aim of study was to determine the effectiveness of high-dose-rate brachytherapy monotherapy for squamous cell carcinoma of lips.

We used a rigid iron needle that were inserted and removed after each fraction. This allows the patient to feel more comfortable between the fractions, it reduced the risk of further infection and allowed to deliver larger doses. 57 patients with histologically confirmed squamous cell carcinoma of lips have been treated with brachytherapy in department of Radiotherapy from 2015 to 2020. Needles are inserted under local anesthesia. The number of needles varied from 2 to 7 depending on the volume of tumor and necessity of prophylactic irradiation of the surrounding tissue. A single dose amounted 8 Gy. Irradiation took place 2 times per week, total of 4 fractions. Mandible viewed as a critical organ. Planning took place after the CT scan. Irradiated volume covered by prescribed dose was equal 10-24 ccm. Graphical method was used for plan optimization.

Swelling after the introduction of needles as a rule disappeared in the evening of the same day, the bleeding stopped in few minutes after discharging. Radiation reaction lasted on average during the month. New young tissue was formed under the crusts. During the seven years of observation no recurrence was revealed. There was no indication of radiation complications.

Conclusions. 32 Gy for 4 fractions, 2 times a week allows to achieve a good local tumor control, reduces the likelihood of infection, which is often observed with the introduction of flexible applicators. Patient well-being between the factions was significantly improved. Radiation complications were not observed in this fractionation regime.

**STUDYING INTO ENVIRONMENTAL WORLD VIEW OF PRIMARY,
SECONDARY AND HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN UKRAINE: A BRIEF
OVERVIEW**

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The study focuses on the phenomenon of environmental world view. In Ukrainian sociological literature, this phenomenon is mostly known as “environmental consciousness” (EC) and considered to be one of the basic concepts in environmental sociology and psychology. Structurally, environmental consciousness consists of three components: *cognitive* (which corresponds to environmental awareness), *emotive* (which is connected with environmental responsiveness) and *conative* (which determines the type of environmental behaviour). As far as the “human–nature” relationship is concerned, there are three main types of EC such as *anthropocentric* (human-centred, which views a human being as dominating all other living creatures, so the natural world is supposed to serve various human needs), *biocentric* (nature-centred, which regards nature as of the greatest value and calls on humans to subordinate themselves to the natural world) and *ecocentric* (which brings to the fore humans’ living in harmony with nature). Taking account of this classification, the author has decided to conduct a pilot survey among students from several Ukrainian schools. The survey was aimed at determining the prevailing type of EC among these students. For this purpose, the following research tools were used: two questionnaires (“How important is nature to you?” and “What are you ready to do for the sake of nature?”), short stories about nature, pictures of beautiful landscapes and those of environmental pollution, a quiz titled “A quick look at the natural world”, etc. The survey lasted from March till November 2021 and covered 48 students from different age groups. The preliminary results indicate a slight prevalence of an ecocentric world view, especially among the students involved in extracurricular environmental activities or attending classes in environmental science. The author also proposes a more detailed classification of environmental consciousness, which includes ten subtypes such as anthropocentric-contemplative, anthropocentric-pragmatic, anthropocentric-destructive, anthropocentric-preserving, biocentric-altruistic, biocentric-syncretic, biocentric-aggressive, ecocentric-rational, ecocentric-constructive and ecocentric-oppositional. This classification is based on a person’s attitude towards nature and his/her activity in the natural environment.

Humanities, Literature & Arts

- *African Studies & History*
- *American Literature & Studies*
- *Asian Studies & History*
- *Canadian Studies & History*
- *Chinese Studies & History*
- *Communication*
- *Drama & Theater Arts*
- *English Language & Literature*
- *Epistemology & Scientific History*
- *Ethnic & Cultural Studies*
- *Feminism & Women's Studies*
- *Film*
- *Foreign Language Learning*
- *French Studies*
- *Gender Studies*
- *History*
- *Humanities, Literature & Arts (general)*
- *Language & Linguistics*
- *Latin American Studies*
- *Literature & Writing*
- *Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies*
- *Music & Musicology*
- *Philosophy*
- *Religion*
- *Sex & Sexuality*
- *Visual Arts*

GRAMMATICAL ASPECT OF STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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The transition to interactive methods of learning English grammar is designed to ensure closer interaction of students with each other in the learning process.

Using interactive learning, we strive to involve all students in the process of learning English grammar, to enable students to exchange knowledge, ideas, ways of activity, to think critically, to make informed decisions. Interactive learning methods: project method, role-playing game, business game, brainstorming, discussions, case study, collaborative learning.

Teaching experience shows that master's grammar training is an important component of the educational process: high-quality knowledge of English. The integrity of the statement depends on the knowledge of the specifics of English grammatical constructions. Knowledge of language material is subject to further training, namely, observation of the grammar phenomenon in the text or specially selected sentences, practical use of grammar material in speech through multiple training and automation of the use of the language phenomenon in speech. It is necessary to fix the rules by repeating the same type of phrases that cause a certain systemic in the brain.

Learning through text gives the opportunity to learn new lexical or grammatical material, learn to communicate, creating communicative situations based on the text. Insufficient time does not allow other approaches to be used for wider study of a foreign language. Therefore, this method is very productive in a non-language technical university. The communicative purpose of grammar learning allows forming a basic requirement for the amount of grammar material to be learned.

Thus, the optimal result in the learning process will be achieved by combining mechanical memorization of rules-formulas and conscious use of appropriate grammatical forms in certain situations. Particular attention is paid to the theory using clarity, its optimal combination with language practice.

The prospect of further research is to find out the factors that contribute to the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of methods of learning foreign language grammar in the conditions of technical higher education.

Life Sciences & Earth Sciences

- *Agronomy & Crop Science*
- *Animal Behavior & Ethology*
- *Animal Husbandry*
- *Atmospheric Sciences*
- *Biochemistry*
- *Biodiversity & Conservation Biology*
- *Bioinformatics & Computational Biology*
- *Biophysics*
- *Biotechnology*
- *Birds*
- *Botany*
- *Cell Biology*
- *Developmental Biology & Embryology*
- *Environmental & Geological Engineering*
- *Environmental Sciences*
- *Evolutionary Biology*
- *Ecology*
- *Food Science & Technology*
- *Forests & Forestry*
- *Geochemistry & Mineralogy*
- *Geology*
- *Hydrology & Water Resources*
- *Insects & Arthropods*
- *Life Sciences & Earth Sciences (general)*
- *Marine Sciences & Fisheries*
- *Microbiology*
- *Molecular Biology*
- *Mycology*
- *Oceanography*
- *Paleontology*
- *Pest Control & Pesticides*
- *Plant Pathology*
- *Proteomics, Peptides & Aminoacids*
- *Soil Sciences*
- *Sustainable Development*
- *Sustainable Energy*
- *Virology*
- *Wood Science & Technology*
- *Zoology*

ВОДА В КЫРГЫЗСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКЕ. ЦЕННОСТЬ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ

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В Кыргызстане насчитывается более 2000 рек длиной свыше 10 км, а общая их длина составляет почти 35 тыс. км. Наиболее крупные реки республики – это реки Нарын (среднегодовой расход 500 куб.м/сек), Талас (25 куб.м/сек), Чу (30 куб.м/сек), Кара-Дарья (120 куб.м/сек), Сары-Джаз (70 куб.м/сек), Чаткал (60 куб.м/сек), Кызыл-Суу (50 куб.м/сек), Сох (40 куб.м/сек), Чон-Кемин (20 куб.м/сек). Примерно 80% питания этих рек происходит за счет таяния ледников и снеговых покровов. Наиболее высокая водность рек КР преобладает в весенне-летний период (Эргешов и Топчубаев, 2017). Это определяет в значительной мере режим стока вод, обуславливает необходимость сооружения объектов ирригации, водно-энергетических узлов, водохранилищ, обеспечивающих своевременную подачу и рациональное использование водных ресурсов с учетом интересов водопользователей Узбекистана, Казахстана и Таджикистана.

Среди стран, где искусственно орошаются сельскохозяйственные земли, Кыргызстан занимает одно из лидирующих мест – 78% (рис. 2). Отмечается и неэффективное использование воды (Эргешов, Топчубаев, 2017).

По материалам статкомитета КР, общий объем стока многоводного года – 57.3 км³. Отток за пределы республики составляет около 45 км³ (78%), при этом вода потребляется соседними государствами Узбекистаном, Казахстаном и Таджикистаном, а также Синьцзян-Уйгурским автономным районом Китая (Zhurankhan et al., 2018; Omarova et al., 2019; Karimov et al., 2019). При этом из общего объема потребления пресной воды в республике расходуется на орошение почти 89%, в промышленности – более 6%, коммунально-бытовом секторе – около 3% и остальная часть – в других видах хозяйственной деятельности (Zhurankhan et al., 2018).

За год 22 км³ воды из кыргызстанских водохранилищ уходит в соседние Узбекистан и Казахстан. Это означает, что 80% накопленной воды уходит соседям. На содержание этих водохранилищ ежегодно из госбюджета выделяются огромные средства. Сегодня наше правительство должно поставить вопрос перед соседними государствами об оплате расходов на содержание водохранилищ. Наши граждане за пользование водой платят, неправильно, что мы не берем с соседей плату за накопленную нами воду, которую они направляют на полив своих полей или других хозяйственных нужд.

В Кыргызстане из-за неграмотно построенных ирригационных систем допускают большие потери воды. Так, уже в начале устья во многих регионах не установлены водораспределительные ирригационные системы (Omarov et al., 2019). Кыргызстан, кроме ирригационного использования, может продавать воду другим странам, и в международной практике цена 1 м³ воды составляет от 0.05 до 0.12 долл. США. Арабские страны обеспечивают население питьевой водой за счет ее импорта из других стран мира. Следует отметить, что Кыргызстан имеет качественную горную воду, и ее с успехом можно экспортировать в те страны, которые нуждаются в ней (Абдымаликов, 2017).

Кыргызстан является действительно «водной державой». Государство должно использовать водные ресурсы в целях экономического развития страны. Реформирование экономического механизма водных отношений должно быть направлено на последовательное развитие принципа платности водопользования на основе гибкого регулирования тарифной политики. Должно быть предусмотрено постепенное достижение самоокупаемости затрат на эксплуатацию и техническое обслуживание водохозяйственных систем с учетом динамики реальной платежеспособности водопользователей.

Сегодня создание и продвижение мирового бренда Кыргызстана по питьевой и лечебной воде является важным. Требуется активно пропагандировать лучшие питьевые и минеральные воды Кыргызстана, что позволит выйти на мировой рынок.

Social Sciences

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ЖЕНСКАЯ ПРЕСТУПНОСТЬ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАЗАХСТАН В ПЕРИОД ПАНДЕМИИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье освещаются вопросы женской преступности в регионах Республики Казахстан в период пандемии, а также причины преступного поведения женщин.

Ключевые слова: женская преступность, Республика Казахстан, пандемия, причины преступности.

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В период карантина характер женской преступности обрел новые криминальные тенденции. Согласно сведениям статистики Генеральной прокуратуры Республики Казахстан, за 11 месяцев 2020 года было совершено 8849 преступлений лицами женского пола, за предыдущий период, а именно 11 месяцев 2019 года ими было совершено 10777 преступлений, что составило снижение на 17,9 % по сравнению с 2019 годом. При этом, в разрезе областей Казахстана, самое большое количество преступлений женщинами было совершено в г. Алматы за 11 месяцев 2020 году – 1181 преступлений, за предыдущий период – 1657 преступлений. Несомненно, что такое количество свойственно данной региону в связи с большой численностью населения в г. Алматы.

Далее, по количеству преступлений, совершенных женщинами можно отнести Алматинскую область, в которой было совершено 1058 преступлений, что составило снижение на 11,2% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом. Достаточно высокое количество преступлений произошло в В-Казахстанской области, в которой было совершено 758 преступлений, что составило снижение на 14,6% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом. В г. Астане (г. Нур-Султан) было совершено 745 преступлений, что составило снижение на 12,2% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом, в котором было совершено 849 преступлений женщинами. В Акмолинской области было совершено 532 преступлений, что составило снижение на 5,3% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом, в котором было совершено 562 преступления женщинами. В Актюбинской области было совершено 300 преступлений, что составило снижение на 32,7% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом, в котором было совершено 446 преступлений женщинами. В Атырауской области было совершено 216 преступлений, что составило снижение на 10,0% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом, в котором было совершено 240 преступления женщинами.

Однако нет сведений в разрезе количества видов преступлений, совершенных женщинами, что усложняет процесс выявления причин и условий совершения преступлений лицами женского пола.

Всего гражданами Республики Казахстан за 11 месяцев 2020 года было совершено 65076 преступлений, что составило снижение на 22,7% по сравнению с предыдущим периодом, в котором было совершено 84153 преступлений казахстанцами.

Выводы: Анализ женской преступности показывает, что в основу ее причин заложены социально-экономические процессы и явления: активное участие женщин в производстве и общественной жизни; ослабление роли социально значимых

институтов, и в первую очередь семьи; возросшая напряженность в обществе, появление в нем конфликтов и враждебности; увеличение числа антиобщественных явлений.

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